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SUN‘IY INTELLEKT

VIDEO TRANSCRIPTION BASED ON HIDDEN MARKOV MODEL

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Abstract. Modeling a signal model for speech recognition in video transcription is a challenging task. Hidden Markov Model gives us great opportunities for speech recognition. Hidden Markov Model is currently the most widely used and successful method for automatic recognition of spoken utterances.

Keywords: Hidden Markov Model, Artificial Neural Networks, control systems, Viterbi algorithm, mathematical models, deep learning.

Speech recognition field is one of the most challenging fields that have faced the scientists from long time. The complete solution is still far from reach. The efforts are concentrated with huge funds from the companies to different related and supportive approaches to reach the final goal. Then, apply it to the enormous applications who are still waiting for the successful speech recognisers that are free from the constraints of speakers, vocabularies and environment. This task is not an easy one due to the interdisciplinary nature of the problem and as it requires speech perception to be implied in the recogniser (Speech Understanding Systems) which in turn strongly pointing to the use of intelligence within the systems [2]. The bare techniques of recognisers (without intelligence) are following wide varieties of approaches with different claims of success by each group of authors who put their faith in their favourite way. However, the sole technique that gain the acceptance of the researchers to be the state of the art is Hidden Markov Model (HMM) technique. HMM is agreed to be the most promising one [3]. It might be used successfully with other techniques to improve the performance, such as hybridising the HMM with Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) algorithms. This doesn't mean that the HMM is pure from approximations that are far from reality, such as the successive observation independence, but the results and the potential of this

algorithm is reliable. The modifications on HMM take the burden of releasing it from these poorly representative approximations hopping for better results [2].

Hidden Markov model. The Hidden Markov model is the basis of a successful set of methods for acoustic modeling in speech recognition systems. The main reasons for this success are related to the ability of this model to analyze speech phenomena and its reliability in practical speech detection systems. The parameters of the Hidden Markov model are usually evaluated at the training stage by maximum probability-based or discriminatory-based learning algorithms using an adequate set of educational data [2]. The core of speech recognition systems based on the Hidden Markov model is the Viterbi algorithm. The Viterbi algorithm uses dynamic programming to determine the best fit between the input speech and the given speech model. In this case, the parameters of the constant Markov model hidden from left to right with N states and M mixtures can be represented by $\lambda = \{\pi, A, B\}$. $\pi = \{\pi_i\}$ - initial state distribution matrix, $A = \{a_{ij}\}$ - probability distribution state matrix. The transition probability is determined by (1) as follows. $a_{ij} = P[q_{t+1} = j | q_t = i]$ the probability of passing through the state i is brought to a state that satisfies the time t in j at time $t + 1$ [1,2].

$$a_{ij} \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^N a_{ij} = 1; 1 \leq i, j \leq N. \quad (1)$$

$B = \{b_j(o_t)\}$ - a set of observational probability densities for each case, which can be represented by a multi-modal Gaussian mixture model [1,2].

$$b_i(o_t) = \sum_{m=1}^M C_{jm} G(o_t, \mu_{jm}, \Sigma_{jm}) \quad (2)$$

Here C_{jm} The mixture coefficient for the m -th mixture in the state j . C_{jm} satisfies the following restrictions:

$$C_{jm} \geq 0, \sum_{m=1}^M C_{jm} = 1; 1 \leq j \leq N, 1 \leq m \leq M. \quad (3)$$

The mean vector $G()$ is a Gaussian distribution with a S_{jm} covariance matrix.

The continuous input speech in the system is divided into frames by a pre-processing module. In the next step, the feature selection module outputs a property vector in each frame to display textual information. Hence, the discrete sequence $O = (o_1, o_2, \dots, o_T)$ of the property vectors (observations) is obtained. In a speech classification task with a dictionary size v , the unknown input speech is compared to the entire Hidden Markov Model by some search algorithms, λ_i and finally, the reference speech with the highest score of the input speech is one of the hidden Markov models. is defined as The Hidden Markov Model is formed in the model by means of a

full search (4) as follows [2,3].

$$LL = P(O | \lambda) = \max_{q_1 q_2 \dots q_T} P[q_1 q_2 \dots q_T, o_1 o_2 \dots o_T | \lambda] = \max_{q_1 q_2 \dots q_T} P[\pi_{q_1} b_{q_1}(o_1) \prod_{t=2}^T a_{q_{t-1} q_t} b_{q_t}(o_t)] \quad (4)$$

Here q_t is the condition at time t . T is the length of the observation sequence. Obviously, as the search area increases, the calculated value increases $O(N^T)$ exponentially. The Viterbi algorithm dynamically outputs the grinding path using a recursive procedure (5).

$$LL_t(j) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq N} [LL_{t-1}(i) a_{ij}] b_j(o_t) \quad (5)$$

Here $LL_t(j)$ is the partial cost function of the grinding path in position j at time t . $LL_{t-1}(i)$ is the estimate of the best path between the possible paths starting from the first case and ending in the i -position at time $t - 1$.

The Viterbi grid diagram is shown in Figure 3. In this case, the horizontal axis represents the time axis of the input speech, and the vertical axis represents the possible cases of the reference Hidden Markov model [1,4].

Figure 3. Viterbi grid diagram.

In systems based on many hidden Markov models, the Viterbi algorithm is the core of the recognition procedure. The Viterbi algorithm is a complete search method that tests all possible solutions to find the best way to match the status sequence between the entered word and the given Hidden Markov model [4].

The use of hidden Markov models for speech recognition has become predominant for the last several years, as evidenced by the number of published papers and talks at major speech conferences. The reasons why this method has become so popular are the inherent statistical (mathematically precise) framework, the ease and availability of training algorithms for estimating the parameters of the models from finite training sets of speech data, the flexibility of the resulting recognition system

where one can easily change the size, type, or architecture of the models to suit particular words, sounds etc., and the ease of implementation of the overall recognition system. However, although hidden Markov model technology has brought speech recognition system performance to new high levels for a variety of applications, there remain some fundamental areas where aspects of the theory are either inadequate for speech, or for which the assumptions that are made do not apply [3]. Examples of such areas range from the fundamental modeling assumption, i.e. that a maximum likelihood estimate of the model parameters provides the best system performance, to issues involved with inadequate training data which leads to the concepts of parameter tying across states, deleted interpolation and other smoothing methods, etc. Other aspects of the basic hidden Markov modeling methodology which are still not well understood include; ways of integrating new features (e.g. prosodic versus spectral features) into the framework in a consistent and meaningful way; the way to properly model sound durations (both within a state and across states of a model); the way to properly use the information in state transitions; and finally the way in which models can be split or clustered as warranted by the training data [4].

References

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